
A Correlation Study of Emotional Maturity among Undergraduate Students in relation to their Academic Procrastination

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17606481>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 19-10-2025

Published: 10-11-2025

Keywords:

*Academic Procrastination,
Emotional Maturity,
Undergraduate Students,
Psychology Background.*

ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the relationship between Emotional Maturity and Academic Procrastination. The subjects in this study were undergraduate psychology background students in Aligarh Muslim University. This study used a correlational quantitative approach with simple random sampling technique, a sample of 105 Psychology background students. This study used a measuring instrument in the form of Emotional Maturity Scale, developed and standardized by Bhardwaj, B. & Dubey, G. (2024) and Academic Procrastination Scale, developed and standardized by Bhardwaj, B. & Dubey, G. (2024), as research instrument to gather data. This study uses a Pearson Product moment analysis technique assisted by a computer program Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 16.0 for windows. The results of the Pearson product moment analysis between Emotional Maturity and Academic Procrastination obtained a correlation coefficient of -0.458 with a significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$) which was accepted, meaning that there was a very significant negative relationship between Emotional Maturity and Academic Procrastination. The effective contribution of the Emotional Maturity

variable given to Academic Procrastination is 20.9%.

Introduction:

A student is someone who is in the process of gaining knowledge at a tertiary institution. When entering college, students will be faced with various activities, namely learning activities, doing assignments given by lecturers and other activities, it is necessary to be able to manage time (Burhan & Herman, 2019). Students must be able to manage themselves when faced with various tasks that exist both on campus and off campus (Fauziah, 2015). In 2020, Indonesia is faced with the Covid-19 pandemic and all learning is carried out online, Rachman and Ririanti (2020) said that online learning is an alternative learning used during the pandemic so that all educators, both lecturers and students in Indonesia, learn online. The online learning is carried out using several applications, namely zoom, google classroom, WhatsApp group, and google meet. Engko and Usmany (2020) in their research on online learning for students, revealed that there were several problems or obstacles that occurred during online learning, namely the lack of internet network, the quota provided by the government was very limited, and sometimes material was not delivered so that students do not understand the explanation of the material. So, with online learning students must be able to study hard and independently and manage time so that it is useful by prioritizing more important activities so that it can make it easier to adjust to existing conditions properly.

Individuals who can prioritize their learning are individuals who are able to process their education as students. According to Djamarah (2002) revealed that there were some students complaining because it was difficult to arrange a schedule or time that should have been done properly but the time was wasted. This is related to the phenomenon of the student learning process which is carried out online, a phenomenon that is often found in education, especially for students, namely that it is not uncommon for students to prioritize other activities over doing assignments, often feeling lazy when doing assignments, and some students do assignments when it's close to the collection deadline. Students who do this can be said to have academic procrastination behaviour or delaying behaviour towards class assignments.

Wicaksono (2017) explains that academic procrastination is the behaviour of delaying academic activities such as ignoring assigned assignments, underestimating easy assignments, carrying out other less useful activities, so that this can have a very detrimental impact on students who do it. The causative factors of individuals who carry out academic procrastination are individuals who do not understand the material presented, there are many deadlines, and individuals are unsure of their abilities (McCloskey, 2011).

Burka and Yuen (Wicaksono, 2017) explain some of the characteristics of individuals who have academic procrastination behaviour including individuals who often postpone assignments so they will not make a problem if the task is done later, have difficulty in making a decision, do not have a plan or design in doing the task.

Researchers conducted interviews with 25 undergraduate psychology students in Aligarh Muslim University getting the result that when studying online, sometimes students are easily distracted by their surroundings, easily get bored and switch to other activities. Online lectures make it difficult for students to manage time between lecture assignments and other activities such as organizations so that when they feel tired and bored with these activities, they choose to do fun activities. When designing assignments, sometimes they don't match the target because they forget, they don't pay close attention to the deadline for assignments, and other reasons, sometimes they do assignments according to their mood, so that assignments are submitted late when this happens, feelings of disappointment and anxiety arise about the grades given by the lecturer. It can be concluded from the results of interviews these students have low academic procrastination behaviour, evidenced by students who have difficulty managing time, easily switch to other things such as fun activities and are late in submitting assignments. The interview results above are related to aspects of academic procrastination described by Ferrari et al. (2013) postponing the moment one is intending to begin studying, postponing the moment that actual studying is to begin, study intention-behaviour discrepancy, and doing things other than studying. If this procrastination behaviour is often carried out by students, it will cause them to be less able to take responsibility for the tasks that are in themselves and will experience losses in their lives. Research conducted by Marwadi (2019) found that students who practice procrastination experience obstacles in graduating from college, this is because students cannot divide their time between lectures and organizations, are lazy and lack motivation.

Patrzek (Sudjianto & Alimbudiono, 2021) explains that students who have procrastination behaviour will more often be dishonest in learning activities, so this can affect students when taking exams in lectures and affect their future when they are already working. Wiyono (2018) explains that there are two factors that can affect procrastination, namely external factors because too many assignments are given, so that students have difficulty determining which tasks to do, and internal factors, namely emotional exhaustion which is the occurrence of internal fatigue. emotions, so that students do their work according to their mood and emotional maturity, that is, students who have not been able to master their emotions will easily give up and be unable to take responsibility for the tasks given. According to Walgito (2010) said that someone who can control good emotions and can control his emotions is someone who has mature emotions so that the individual can think maturely when facing a problem. Rai & Khanal (2017) revealed

emotional maturity, which is an ability that exists in individuals when facing and responding to positive circumstances by controlling emotions appropriately and being able to behave rationally. Walgito (2010) describes aspects of emotional maturity, namely being able to accept one's condition with other people, not being impulsive, being able to control emotions, thinking objectively, and being able to be responsible.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To find the extent level of Academic Procrastination among undergraduate students.
2. To find the extent level of Emotional Maturity among undergraduate students.
3. To find the extent of relationship of Emotional Maturity with Academic Procrastination among undergraduate students.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:

The researchers formulate null hypotheses in the present study for testing purposes. They are as:

H.01: Undergraduate students would have moderate level of Academic Procrastination.

H.02: Undergraduate students would have moderate level of Emotional Maturity.

H0.3: There is no significant relationship of Emotional Maturity with Academic Procrastination among undergraduate students.

METHOD:

For the current study, the researcher utilized a descriptive research design and gathered data from 105 Undergraduate Psychology background students from Psychology Department of Aligarh Muslim University using a simple random sampling method.

RESEARCH VARIABLES:

The present research is a correlation study that thought about the criteria of descriptive research and depends on one factor namely as, Emotional Maturity and another Variable namely as, Academic Procrastination.

RESEARCH TOOLS:

The following are research tools used by the researcher in this study:

(I). Emotional Maturity Scale-

Emotional Maturity Scale developed and standardized by Bhardwaj, B. and Dubey, G. (2024), It has five dimensions consisting of 38 items. The content validity was measured by the experts and the r value of construct validity ranges from 0.46-0.89. The reliability of the scale was measured with the help of Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient and the values are 0.91.

(II). Academic Procrastination Scale-

Academic Procrastination Scale developed and standardized by Bhardwaj, B. and Dubey, G. (2024), It has four dimensions consisting of 36 items. The content validity was measured by the experts and the r value of construct validity ranges from 0.59-0.92. The reliability of the scale was measured with the help of Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient and Spearman-Brown prophecy formula and the values are 0.93 and 0.91 respectively. For getting accurate results as well as to save time the analysis was done through SPSS software.

PROCEDURE:

Initially, the researchers obtained permission from the school authorities to conduct the research. Subsequently, participants were informed about the study's objectives and asked for their consent to participate. They were then instructed to carefully read the questionnaire and select the options that accurately reflected their attitudes. The Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS) and Academic Procrastination Scale (APS) was then administered to gauge the correlation of Emotional Maturity with students' Academic Procrastination separately.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES:

Mean, SD, 't' test and coefficient of correlation (r) were used to assess the extent of level and relationship of Emotional Maturity with Academic Procrastination among undergraduates.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION:

The collected data was analysed both quantitatively. Based on the results of the assumption test from the normality test, it can be seen that the results of the normality index (K-SZ) for the Academic

Procrastination variable are 1.298 with a significance level (p) of 0.069 ($p > 0.05$) so that the Academic Procrastination variable is normally distributed.

In the Emotional Maturity variable, the normality index (K-SZ) is 1.145 with a significance level (p) of 0.145 ($p > 0.05$), so the Emotional Maturity variable can be normally distributed. It can be concluded that there is no difference in the distribution of data between the sample and the population so that the data can be normally distributed. The results of the normality test can be seen in table 1.

Table.1: Normality of the Data

Variable	(K-S) Z score	Sig.	Results
Academic Procrastination	1.298	0.069	Normally Distributed
Emotional Maturity	1.145	0.145	Normally Distributed

OBJECTIVE-1: To find the extent level of Academic Procrastination among undergraduate students.

To study the extent level of Academic Procrastination among undergraduate students, the following research hypothesis was formulated:

H.01. Undergraduate students would have moderate level of Academic Procrastination.

To test the above research hypothesis, Mean, Standard Deviation, and level of significance of the scores obtained from the Academic Procrastination scale were calculated. The results are presented in Table-2.

Table.2: Categorization of Academic Procrastination Variables

Variable	Categorization	Frequency	Percentage
Academic Procrastination	High	19	18%
	Moderate	78	74%
	Low	8	8%
	Total	105	100%

In the table above, it can be seen that in the categorization of Academic Procrastination scores of Psychology Undergraduate students obtained those 19 students (18%) had Academic Procrastination behaviour in the high category, 78 students (74%) had Academic Procrastination behaviour in the

moderate category and 8 students (8%) have Academic Procrastination behaviour in the low category. Based on the explanation of the results above, it can be analysed that Psychology Undergraduate students have Academic Procrastination behaviour in the moderate category.

OBJECTIVE-2: To find the extent level of Emotional Maturity among undergraduate students.

To study the extent level of Emotional Maturity among undergraduate students., the following research hypothesis was formulated:

H. 02: Undergraduate students would have moderate level of Emotional Maturity.

To test the above research hypothesis, Mean, Standard Deviation, t-value and level of significance of the scores obtained from the Emotional Maturity scale were calculated. The results are presented in Table-3.

Table.3: Categorization of Emotional Maturity Variables

Variable	Categorization	Frequency	Percentage
Emotional Maturity	High	6	6%
	Moderate	96	91%
	Low	3	3%
	Total	105	100%

In the table above, it can be seen that in the categorization of Emotional Maturity scores of Psychology Undergraduate students was found that 6 students (6%) had Emotional Maturity in the high category, 96 students (91%) had Emotional Maturity in medium category and 3 students (3%) have Emotional Maturity in the low category. Based on the explanation of the results above, it is known that Psychology S1 students Aligarh Muslim University. have a moderate level of Emotional Maturity.

OBJECTIVE-3: To find the extent of relationship of Emotional Maturity with Academic Procrastination among undergraduate students.

For the purpose of studying the relationship between Emotional Maturity with Academic Procrastination among undergraduate students, the following null hypothesis was formulated:

H03. There is no significant relationship of Emotional Maturity with Academic Procrastination among undergraduate students.

To test the above Null Hypothesis, Pearson Product moment Correlation and level of significance of the scores obtained from the Emotional Maturity scale and Academic Procrastination scale were calculated. The results are presented in Table-4.

Table.4: categorization of Academic Procrastination and Emotional Maturity Variables

Variable	Pearson correlation	Sig level (p)	Information
Emotional Maturity with Academic Procrastination	-0.458	0.000	Significant

**** Significant at 0.01 level.**

The results of the Pearson product moment correlation analysis, hypothesis test between Emotional Maturity and Academic Procrastination obtained a correlation coefficient of -0.458 with a significance level 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). It can be concluded that the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is a significant negative relationship between Emotional Maturity and Academic Procrastination, where the higher the Emotional Maturity, the lower the Academic Procrastination. Conversely, the lower the Emotional Maturity, the higher the Academic Procrastination. The effective contribution in testing this hypothesis can be seen in the correlation coefficient which is squared then multiplied by 100%, the calculation is $(-0.458)^2 \times 100\% = 20.9\%$, then an effective contribution of 20.9% is obtained.

DISCUSSION:

The results of the analysis using the product moment obtained a correlation coefficient of 0.458 with a significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), meaning that the hypothesis is accepted because the two variables have a very significant negative relationship between Emotional Maturity and Academic Procrastination. The higher the Emotional Maturity, the lower the Academic Procrastination and conversely the lower the Emotional maturity, the higher the Academic Procrastination that is owned by the psychology undergraduate students at Aligarh Muslim University. Based on the effective contribution given by Emotional Maturity of 20.9% to Academic Procrastination in students, the remaining 79.1% is influenced by other variables not discussed in this study.

CONCLUSION:

Based on the results of the analysis of research data that has been carried out by researchers at undergraduate Psychology students Aligarh Muslim University., it can be concluded that. There is a very significant negative relationship between emotional maturity and academic procrastination in Psychology undergraduate students Aligarh Muslim University. The higher the Emotional Maturity of students, the lower the Academic Procrastination. Conversely, the lower the Emotional Maturity of students, the higher the Academic Procrastination of these students. The effective contribution given by Emotional Maturity to Academic Procrastination is 20.9 %. The researcher hopes that in future research they can carry out the process of collecting data directly or face to face, so that they can directly monitor the subject when filling out the scale to minimize the occurrence of reckless filling of the scale. With this research, it can be used as a reference or reference as new research that will examine the relationship between Emotional Maturity and Academic Procrastination in students, which has not been widely studied and found in other studies. Students are expected to be able to increase and maintain their Emotional Maturity such as a sense of responsibility in lecture assignments so as to avoid Academic Procrastination behaviour.

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